

The weakening of „dark energy” as the inevitable consequence of the hypothetical gravitational polarisation of the quantum vacuum

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Abstract: New results from the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) collaboration strongly suggest that 'dark energy', the unknown content of the Universe, does not act as a cosmological constant. In fact, it appears that the impact of 'dark energy' is weakening over time. This is contrary to our current best cosmological model, the Λ CDM cosmology. We present the intriguing result that the weakening of "dark energy" is an inevitable consequence of the hypothetical gravitational polarisation of the quantum vacuum. In other words, the evolving 'dark energy' is an inherent part of the emerging Gravitational Polarisation Quantum Vacuum (GP-QV) cosmology. This should not be viewed as an explanation of the DESI results or as proof of GP-QV cosmology, but rather as a possibility that merits further investigation.

1. Introduction

Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument¹(DESI) is an international experiment involving more than 900 scientists from over 70 institutions around the world. Using data from its first three years of observations (including nearly 15 million of the best-measured galaxies and quasars), DESI has produced the largest 3D map of the Universe to date, making it possible to track the influence of dark energy over the past 11 billion years. The DESI data combined with information from studies of the cosmic microwave background, supernovae, and weak gravitational lensing, suggest more strongly than a year ago that the impact of “dark energy” may be weakening over time [1-3]. If confirmed by future larger data sets, this will be a breakthrough in our understanding of the contents of the Universe and its evolution.

Before going any further, it should be noted that the DESI result is only one of a growing number of potential challenges to standard Λ CDM cosmology. One of these is the striking preliminary result from the ALPHA-g collaboration at CERN. According to this preliminary result from the ALPHA-g experiment [4], antiatoms fall *with less acceleration* than atoms in the Earth's gravitational field; more precisely the gravitational acceleration of antiatoms is $g_{\bar{a}} = 7.4^{+2.1}_{-2.1} m/s^2$, instead of $g = 9.81 m/s^2$ for atoms. A plausible interpretation of the possible different gravitational acceleration of antinucleons and nucleons is their inner structure, i.e. a different content of antiquarks and quarks [5]. This (strengthened by the theoretical result of Villata [6]) suggests that quarks and antiquarks may have gravitational charges of opposite sign [7], i.e. that a quark-antiquark pair is a gravitational dipole. Therefore, the current ALPHA-g result is a small encouragement for the GP-QV Cosmology, which will be applied to the DESI results below.

In this paper we point out that the weakening of "dark energy" is an inevitable consequence of the hypothetical gravitational polarisation of the quantum vacuum, i.e. an inevitable consequence of

¹ <https://www.desi.lbl.gov/>

the emerging GP-QV cosmology. At this stage, it is absolutely premature to regard this as anything more than an intriguing coincidence that deserves further attention and study. If "dark energy" is shown to behave like a cosmological constant, it will be an incontrovertible argument against GP-QV cosmology. If it is confirmed that "dark energy" evolves over time, it will not prove GP-QV cosmology, but it will make it much more plausible.

The essence of GP-QV cosmology (see the recent review [7] and references therein, as well as [8,9]) is that the only contents of the Universe are the quantum vacuum, "enriched" with virtual gravitational dipoles², and the Standard Model Matter immersed in it. We call Standard Model Matter the ordinary matter composed of quarks and leptons (and corresponding antiquarks and antileptons) interacting through the exchange of gauge bosons.

In short, as outlined below, GP-QV cosmology explains phenomena usually attributed to dark matter and dark energy as local and global effects of the gravitationally polarised quantum vacuum. Galaxies do not have dark matter halos, but polarised quantum vacuum halos, which locally explain the dynamics of the galaxy. Globally, all polarised quantum vacuum halos are a cosmological fluid that is currently in an epoch of negative pressure, causing the current accelerated expansion of the Universe. For the first time, the quantum vacuum is proposed as a replacement for both dark matter and dark energy.

If gravitational dipoles (with a non-zero gravitational dipole moment \mathbf{p}_g) exist, the gravitational polarization density \mathbf{P}_g , i.e. the gravitational dipole moment per unit volume, can be attributed to the quantum vacuum. It is obvious that the magnitude of the gravitational polarization density \mathbf{P}_g satisfies the inequality $0 \leq P_g \leq P_{gmax}$, where 0 corresponds to random orientation of dipoles, while the maximal magnitude P_{gmax} corresponds to the case of saturation (when all dipoles are aligned with the external field). The value P_{gmax} must be a universal constant related to the gravitational properties of the quantum vacuum; a rough approximation is $P_{gmax} = 3/16\pi (kg/m^2)$. Note that the magnitude of a single gravitational dipole in the quantum vacuum must be less than \hbar/c .

If the external gravitational field is zero, quantum vacuum may be considered as a fluid of randomly oriented gravitational dipoles. In this case, the gravitational polarization density is equal to zero ($\mathbf{P}_g \equiv 0$); of course, such a vacuum is not a source of gravitation.

However, the random orientation of virtual dipoles can be broken by the gravitational field of the immersed Standard Model matter. Massive bodies (particles, stars, planets, black holes, . . .) but also many-body systems such as galaxies are surrounded by an invisible halo of gravitationally polarized quantum vacuum, i.e. a region of non-random orientation of virtual gravitational dipoles ($\mathbf{P}_g \neq 0$). The *spatial variation* of the gravitational polarization density generates a *gravitational bound charge density* of the quantum vacuum:

$$\rho_{qv} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}_g \quad (1)$$

This gravitational bound charge density is in fact an effective gravitational charge density, which acts as if there is a real non-zero gravitational charge. That is how the magic of the gravitational polarisation of the quantum vacuum works; quantum vacuum is a source of gravity, thanks to the immersed Standard Model matter.

Because of our very limited understanding of the quantum vacuum, the only way to find a solution to the fundamental equation (1) is to consider the quantum vacuum as a cosmological fluid composed of non-interacting gravitational dipoles, i.e. an ideal gas of virtual gravitational dipoles.

In the case of a single point-like body of mass M_b , the simplest approximation for the effective gravitational charge of the quantum vacuum within a sphere of radius r is:

² The possibilities that quantum vacuum fluctuations behave as gravitational dipoles are discussed in the Appendix.

$$M_{qv}(M_b, r) = 4\pi P_{gmax} r^2 \tanh\left(\frac{R_{sat}}{r}\right) f_g\left(\frac{R_{ran}}{r}\right);$$

$$R_{sat} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{M_b}{4\pi P_{gmax}}} \text{ and } R_{ran} = \alpha_g R_{sat} \quad (2)$$

The choice of the interpolating function $f_g(R_{ran}/r)$ is not unique, but (see [7-9]) it should be strictly decreasing function of r (i.e. strictly increasing function of ratio R_{ran}/r) with the following behaviour for small and large r :

$$f_g\left(\frac{R_{ran}}{r}\right) \approx 1 \text{ for } r \ll R_{ran} \quad \text{and} \quad f_g\left(\frac{R_{ran}}{r}\right) \approx \frac{R_{ran}}{r} \text{ for } r \gg R_{ran} \quad (3)$$

A rough working approximation of such a function used in the previous work [8-10] is:

$$f_g\left(\frac{R_{ran}}{r}\right) = \tanh\left(\frac{R_{ran}}{r}\right) \quad (4)$$

Already for $r > R_{ran}$ (or formally in the limit $r \rightarrow \infty$) equation (2) with accompanying equations (3) and (4) leads to:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} M_{qv}(M_b, r) = \alpha_g M_b \equiv M_{qvmax}(M_b) \quad (5)$$

In equation (5), $M_{qvmax}(M_b)$ denotes the maximum of the effective gravitational charge of the quantum vacuum that can be induced by the gravitational field of a point-like body of mass M_b ; this gives clear physical meaning to the dimensionless (potentially fundamental) constant α_g .

Roughly speaking, according to equations (2) and (3), the halo of the gravitationally polarised quantum vacuum around a point-like body has three regions, roughly defined by R_{sat} and R_{ran} . The first region (inside a sphere with a characteristic radius R_{sat}) is a saturation dominated region, i.e. a region with almost complete alignment of the gravitational dipoles with the gravitational field of the point-like body. Far away from the body (outside a sphere of characteristic radius R_{ran}) there is a region where the random orientation of the dipoles dominates. Between the region of saturation and the region of random orientation there is a region of partial (incomplete) alignment of the gravitational dipoles. In GP-QV cosmology, this second region successfully explains phenomena that are usually attributed to hypothetical dark matter or to the modification of gravity.

It is important to understand that very often bodies are prevented from having a large halo of the polarised quantum vacuum. For example, our Earth, with $R_{sat} \approx 2.8 \times 10^{12}$ (almost 19 AU) and R_{ran} at least an order of magnitude larger, could in principle have a halo the size of our Solar System. However, this is prevented by the much stronger gravitational field of the Sun, which aligns the dipoles in its direction; if moved to the edge of the Solar System, our Earth would have a much larger halo, with a greater effective gravitational charge of the quantum vacuum.

In principle, if there is a system of bodies and the distances between the bodies increase (as is the case in our expanding Universe), the size of the halos and the amount of effective gravitational charge of the quantum will also increase. An increase in the effective gravitational charge, i.e. an increase in a cosmological fluid, means negative pressure and the potential for accelerated expansion. However, if all bodies form almost complete halos of size R , the further increase in effective gravitational charge is much smaller and tends to zero.

Alternatively, if we consider hydrogen and helium gas before the formation of the first stars and galaxies, instead of talking about individual halos of the polarised quantum vacuum, we can assign to the nuclei a variable gravitational mass that increases with the rarefaction of the gas (i.e. the expansion of the Universe). At high rarefaction, however, the increase in gravitational charge becomes insignificant, and we can consider a hydrogen and helium gas with nuclei having a gravitational charge α_g times their mass, which can ensure, among other things, the very rapid formation of structures without dark matter.

This alternative picture can also be a useful mental image in the case of a universe rich in stars and galaxies.

Qualitatively, this is the same as suggested by the DESI data. In the next section we will try to get some rough analytical and numerical insights using a toy model.

2. A (hopefully enlightening) toy model of the Universe

The toy model introduced in this section is the distribution of matter at the sites of an expanding (i.e. dynamical) simple cubic lattice with periodic boundary conditions; a simplification without which an illustrative analytical calculation is unfortunately not possible.

Consider the Universe as a simple cubic lattice with a *variable* side R (mimicking the scale factor of the Universe) containing a very large number of sites $N_{tot} = N \times N \times N$, each occupied by a point-like body of the same mass M_b . Thus, the total Standard Model mass on the lattice is equal to $M_{tot} = N_{tot}M_b$ (and it mimics the total mass M_{SMU} of the Standard Model matter in the Universe). To ensure that the Universe looks the same from each body, we assume periodic boundary conditions, as is usually done in statistical models (such as the Ising model) on a lattice.

Each site of the lattice (i.e. each point-like body on the site) is at the centre of a halo of the polarised quantum vacuum around it. All these halos are identical in shape, size and effective gravitational charge. If the halos are approximated by spheres of radius R_h , according to the above equations, the total effective gravitational charge $M_{qvU}(N, R)$ of the quantum vacuum in the Universe can be approximated by:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{qvU}(N, R) &= N^3 M_{qv}(M_b, R_h) \\ &= N^3 4\pi P_{gmax} R_h^2 \tanh\left(\frac{R_{sat}(M_b)}{R_h}\right) \tanh\left(\alpha_g \frac{R_{sat}(M_b)}{R_h}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The crucial step now is to express the local variables R_h and $R_{sat}(M_b) \equiv \sqrt{M_b/4\pi P_{gmax}}$, with the global variables R and N . The distance between two neighbouring sites is $d = R/N$, while the size of a halo cannot be larger than $d/2$. So, we can write $R_h = R/2N$. On the other hand, M_b in $R_{sat}(M_b)$ can be replaced by M_{SMU}/N^3 . Using $R_h = R/2N$ and $M_b = M_{SMU}/N^3$, equation (6) for the total effective gravitational charge of the Universe can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{qvU}(N, R) &= \pi P_{gmax} N R^2 \tanh\left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R}\right) \tanh\left(\alpha_g \frac{2}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R}\right) \\ &\text{with } R_{satU} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{M_{SMU}}{4\pi P_{gmax}}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

If we consider the gravitationally polarised quantum vacuum as a cosmological fluid, we can formally determine its pressure:

$$p_{qvU}(N, R) = -c^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial V_U} M_{qvU}(N, R) \quad (8)$$

Note that $V_U = R^3$ mimics the volume of the Universe (which is otherwise $V_U = 2\pi^2 R^3$ in a closed Universe). The end result of a somewhat lengthy but elementary derivation is

$$p_{qvU}(N, R) = -\frac{2}{3} \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\sinh\left(\frac{4}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R}\right)} \frac{4}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\sinh\left(\frac{4\alpha_g}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R}\right)} \frac{4\alpha_g}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R} \right] \rho_{qvU} c^2 \quad (9)$$

Of course, in today's Universe, which is well described by the words "the cosmic web", the model leading to equation (9) is absolutely a toy model. However, it is much closer to the Universe before the formation of the first stars and galaxies, when the Universe was a gas of hydrogen and helium, and the only point-like bodies were atoms (or just nuclei) of hydrogen and helium.

The period when the expanding Universe was a gas of hydrogen and helium is characterised by the largest N ; the total number of atoms, corresponding to the mass of the visible Universe today, is roughly of the order of 10^{81} , and in the above equation $\sqrt{N} \sim 10^{13}$. The number of atoms in the gas (i.e. the number of sites in our lattice) remains virtually constant until the first stars and galaxies form. Formation of stars and galaxies brings a dramatic fall in the number N^3 of point like bodies (note that a star like our Sun contains equivalent of about 10^{57} initial atoms of hydrogen, and if all the gas were converted into stars like the Sun, the number N^3 would fall from 10^{81} to 10^{24}).

Note that equation (9) has the following structure, which facilitates analysis:

$$p_{qvU}(N, R) = -\frac{2}{3} \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{x}{\sinh(x)} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\alpha_g x}{\sinh(\alpha_g x)} \right] \rho_{qvU} c^2, \quad \text{with } x \equiv \frac{4}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R} \quad (10)$$

The important feature of x in equation (10) is that its value is the same whether the three values (N, R, R_{satU}) used for the calculation correspond to the whole Universe or to the visible Universe. It is easy to see that if R for the whole Universe is B times larger than R_v for the visible Universe, the same is true for N , while R_{satU} (see its definition in Eq. (7)) is $B^{3/2}$ times larger (because the mass is B^3 times larger). Different constants of proportionality (but all expressed by B) cancel in the equation for x ; hence the value of x remains unchanged in the transformation of variables from the whole to the visible Universe.

Mathematically speaking

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x}{\sinh(x)} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x}{\sinh(x)} = 0 \quad (11)$$

However, the relations (11) are already approximately true if x is only a few times smaller or larger than 1. For example, if $x = 0.2$ and $x = 5$, the corresponding values of $x/\sinh(x)$ are 0.993 and 0.067, respectively, which are close to the limits in equations (11).

Let us apply the above results from our toy model to the expanding universe when it was a gas dominated by hydrogen, with a smaller proportion of helium.

For a constant N , as follows from Eq. (10), x decreases with R , from a value significantly greater than 1 (hence $x/\sinh(x) \approx 0$) to values significantly less than 1 (i.e. $x/\sinh(x) \approx 1$). According to Eq. (10), this means that as the universe expands, the quantum vacuum as a cosmological fluid (which replaces dark energy in GP-QV cosmology) is transformed from an initial fluid with significant negative pressure to a pressureless fluid.

Apparently, at the beginning of the formation of stars and galaxies, x was very small. Consequently, according to equations (9) and (10), the quantum vacuum was a pressureless cosmological fluid, but according to Eq. (7) its effective gravitational charge was α_g times greater than the mass of the Standard Model matter. The expansion of our universe was not accelerating but decelerating, and the question is what caused the accelerated expansion rather than the recollapse of the then gaseous structureless Universe.

The intriguing answer suggested by our toy model is this: The formation of stars and galaxies prevented the recollapse and triggered the accelerated expansion of our Universe. Indeed, according to equation (10), as N decreases (due to the formation of stars and galaxies), x increases and can

become sufficiently larger than 1, transforming the pressureless quantum vacuum into a cosmological fluid with a significant negative pressure.

Of course, the decrease of N cannot be infinite, and after the stabilisation of N around a new constant value, x decreases again as R increases. In a way, there is a similarity between what happened during the expansion of the Universe without structure and what happens during the expansion of the Universe with structure; in both cases, the quantum vacuum changes from a cosmological fluid with a strong negative pressure to a pressureless fluid.

2.1 Numerical illustrations

Of course, good numerical results cannot be expected from the toy model presented, but it may be useful to see what they indicate.

Let us use data from the Particle Data Group [10], in particular from the Astronomical Constants and Parameters table³ and the Cosmological Parameters review⁴.

According to [11], the current density of baryonic matter (i.e. the matter of the Standard Model) and the size of the visible Universe are respectively:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_{b0} &\approx 4.9 \times 10^{-28} \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ R_{vU0} &\approx 46.5 \text{ ly} = 4.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

Using the above data we can calculate the Standard Model mass of the Universe (M_{SMU}), and the saturation radius of the Universe (R_{satU}) and number of nucleons (N^3) corresponding to this mass.

$$\begin{aligned}M_{SMU} &= \frac{4\pi}{3} R_{vU0}^3 \rho_{b0} \approx 1.7 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg} \\ R_{satU} &= \sqrt{\frac{M_{SMU}}{4\pi P_{gmax}}} \approx 4.75 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}\end{aligned}\tag{13}$$

$$N^3 = \frac{M_{SMU}}{m_p} = \frac{1.7 \times 10^{53}}{1.67 \times 10^{-27}} \approx 10^{80}, N \approx 4.6 \times 10^{26}, \sqrt{N} \approx 2.1 \times 10^{13}$$

Note that (neglecting the fact that a fraction of the nuclei are not hydrogen but helium) the number N^3 in equation (13) can be used as the number of point-like bodies in the Universe before the formation of the first stars and galaxies.

Now, the first question is when is $x > 1$. The answer, based on the results in equation (13) is

$$x \equiv \frac{4}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{R_{satU}}{R} > 1 \implies R < \frac{4R_{satU}}{\sqrt{N}} \approx 1.6 \times 10^{14} \text{ m} \approx 1000 \text{ AU}\tag{14}$$

So our toy model suggests (very questionably, of course) an accelerated acceleration when the universe was smaller than 1000 astronomical units and in the state of plasma. But it remains an intriguing suggestion.

After that (and especially between the birth of the cosmic microwave background and the formation of stars and galaxies, $x \ll 1$, with the quantum vacuum as a pressureless fluid.

The second question is whether the formation of structures can trigger accelerated expansion of the Universe. For this it is necessary that

$$\sqrt{N} < 4 \frac{R_{satU}}{R}\tag{15}$$

³ https://pdg.lbl.gov/2024/reviews/contents_sports.html

⁴ https://pdg.lbl.gov/2024/reviews/contents_sports.html

For example, assuming $R_{satU}/R = 25$ (i.e. redshift $z \approx 25$), this is possible when $N^3 \approx 10^{12}$ which is approximately the number of galaxies in the present Universe, and thus not far from the number of entities in the Universe that can be considered as point-like bodies in our toy model.

3. Outlook

In conclusion, there are intriguing indications that there may be a deep relationship between GP-QV cosmology and DESI results, but unfortunately in a situation where precise analytical results are impossible, the current toy model considerations should be followed by complex numerical studies and simulations.

It should be noted that the results in equations (13) are obtained in the framework of Λ CDM cosmology and may be different in GP-QV cosmology. Consequently, the results obtained from equations (14) and (15) may be more favourable.

Finally, let us point out a problem common to all alternative theories, a problem that in principle slows down our understanding of the Universe. To a greater or lesser extent, all alternative models suffer from a lack of development compared to the standard Λ CDM cosmology, because many of these alternative ideas are in the hands of very few individuals who cannot produce results at the same speed as the thousands of researchers working on the Standard model.

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Appendix

How the quantum vacuum fluctuations can be virtual gravitational dipoles

The question “What if the quantum vacuum fluctuations are virtual gravitational dipoles?” has two very different facets. From the perspective of General relativity and the Standard Model of particles and fields, it is meaningless. The existence of any kind of gravitational dipole is so unlikely that it does not merit scientific attention. This negative attitude completely prevents thinking about the intriguing consequences of the working hypothesis that the quantum vacuum fluctuations are virtual gravitational dipoles. In short, apparently meaningful implications [7-9, 11] are rejected because of an apparently meaningless hypothesis.

Before we continue, it is useful to point to the following cautious and illuminating comment often given in the previous studies (for example see [9]): “*Let us introduce the working hypothesis that, by their nature, quantum vacuum fluctuations are virtual gravitational dipoles. Apparently, the simplest and the most elegant realization of this hypothesis is if particles and antiparticles have gravitational charge of the opposite sign; of course, nature may surprise us with a different realization of the gravitational dipole-like behaviour of the quantum vacuum.*”

Therefore, the physical nature of virtual gravitational dipoles is an open question. For the vast majority who are "allergic" to the idea of "classical" gravitational dipoles composed of gravitational charges of opposite signs⁵, the next section of this Appendix demonstrates the possibility of gravitational dipole-like behaviour of the quantum vacuum fluctuations if gravitational charge can only be positive.

A.1 The gravitational polarisation of the quantum vacuum resulting from the inclusion of gravity in the Standard Model of particles and fields.

The following symmetry group was very recently used [12] to incorporate gravitation as the fourth fundamental interaction within the Standard Model of particles and fields.

$$G_{SMg} = \frac{\left[\frac{SU(3)_c \times U(1)_g}{Z_3} \right] \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y}{Z_6} \quad (A.1)$$

The term in the square brackets in the above symmetry group is decomposition of group $U(3)_{cg}$ that unifies strong force and gravity respectively described by $SU(3)_c$ and $U(1)_g$ symmetry groups, i.e. $U(3)_{cg} = SU(3)_c \times U(1)_g / Z_3$. The Gravitational Charge is defined as the Trace of the Energy-Momentum tensor, which is the Lorentz-invariant physical quantity that has a non-zero value for all the fundamental particles of the Standard Model, thereby ensuring the universality of gravitational interaction. The $U(1)_g$ gravity is mediated by a massless, gravitationally charged gauge boson called the 'graviboson'. The masslessness of the graviboson ensures that gravity is long-range, while its gravitational charge ensures that it is nonlinear.

The key point is that the group $U(1)_g$ defines the gravitational state of each quantum vacuum fluctuation via the gravitational phase $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ or the unit vector $e^{i\theta}$.

⁵ Which is in fact, as discussed in Introduction, encouraged by the preliminary results of the ALPHA-g experiment.

Figure 1 : The unit circle (S^1) of $U(1)_g$ phases centred at the origin of the complex plane, with a radius of 1. This circle represents the Group $U(1)_g$, i.e. the set of all possible "rotational states" that gravitational symmetry can take.

It is easy to visualize the gravitational state of a single quantum vacuum fluctuation using a unit circle in the complex plane as representation of the $U(1)_g$ group. In this representation (see Figure 1), every point on the unit circle corresponds to a possible *internal state* of a vacuum fluctuation.

The existence of internal states of quantum vacuum fluctuations, described by unit vectors behaving as 'gravitational spin' within an external gravitational field, converts these fluctuations into gravitational dipoles. Therefore, in $U(1)_g$ gravity, there are gravitational dipoles without opposite gravitational charges.

In principle, we must transition from individual unit vectors to the collective vector quantity \mathbf{P}_{gi} , which describes quantum vacuum fluctuations within a volume V :

$$\mathbf{P}_{gi} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{k \in V} e^{i\theta_k} \quad (A.2)$$

The vector \mathbf{P}_{gi} is the vector sum of all the individual unit vectors within a volume V , and the index i reminds us that it is a vector in internal (topological) space. Its counterpart in real space, the Gravitational Polarization Density of the quantum vacuum, \mathbf{P}_g , describes the quantum vacuum as a source of gravity, with the effective gravitational charge density determined via the fundamental relation $\rho_{qv} = -\nabla \mathbf{P}_g$ which is independent of the physical nature of gravitational dipoles.